

Appendix S4. Estimating cross-environment genetic correlations.

We estimated the genetic correlation for trait expression across the field and greenhouse environments by resampling breeding values from each within-environment model. Specifically, we resampled F_2 (parents of the F_3 experimental population) breeding values from 2000 stored posteriors and subsequently generated a distribution of cross-environment genetic correlation values (r_{Aij} ; where i and j represent either the greenhouse or field environment). This approach incorporated the uncertainty around the breeding values into the estimation of r and its credibility intervals, thus permitting tests of significance in a conservative manner despite additive covariances not being accounted for in the model. (Grieshop et al. 2021).

$$r_{Aij} = \frac{Cov_{Aij}}{\sqrt{(V_{Ai})(V_{Aj})}}$$

We estimated the cross-environment genetic correlation (r_A) using the approach above because models that included data from both environments and that attempted to estimate the 3 components of cross-environment covariance had issues of convergence and autocorrelation. In reference, these ‘full’ models specified a “us(environment):animal” structure in the model, where “us()” estimates the covariance between environments (Hadfield, 2019). To provide confidence that our approach of estimating r_A from separate environmental models did not differ from the approach using cross-environment models, we estimated r_A using both approaches but in models that excluded the dominance variance component. By removing dominance variance and only estimating within-environment variances using the “idh()” function, we were able to produce models passing diagnostic tests. In these cross-environment models, we also set environment and block nested within block as fixed effects. Models were run for 2,100,000 iterations with a 100,000 burn-in storing samples every 1000 iterations.

LITERATURE CITED

- Grieshop, K., P. L. Maurizio, G. Arnqvist, and D. Berger. 2021. Selection in males purges the mutation load on female fitness. *Evolution Letters* 5: 328–343.
- Hadfield, J. 2019. MCMCglmm Course Notes. *R-CRAN*.